

UNDERSTANDING CUSTOMER EXPECTATION IN FACIAL TREATMENT SERVICES IN MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to measure the relationship of service quality, brand image, trust and price towards customer satisfaction in a facial treatment services. Facial treatment services are getting more popular as customer are more concern about their looking and appearances. It was also due to the increase of awareness on the important of taking care of personal beauty. The study used questionnaires in data collection. Data was collected through google form based on the list name given by the service providers. 500 name list was gathered and participated in the data distribution. Only 256 complete and useable data returns for data analysis. The results indicate that factors lead to customer satisfaction are service quality, brand image and trust. It was highlighted that price does not significant towards customer satisfaction. Such new findings can be used by the service providers to think off on their new marketing strategy and campaign. It also means that certain customer is actually does not bother about the prices as long as the service provided meet their expectations and needs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global rapid growth of facial treatment propelled this study to assess the influence of customer satisfaction on service quality in facial treatment. As customers today are more concerned about their appearance, they are willing to pay more for different types of beauty products and services[1]. There are different facial treatment styles available. Facial treatment comes with a number of products and services to make skin clear, clean, and radiant[2]. Women are not the only ones who have demand for facial treatment but there are demands for facial treatment among men too because they have daily shaving routine that causes bumps and irritations on their skin. The cleaning process during facial treatment leads to a smoother and healthier skin[3].

Studies have revealed that daily facial treatment has numerous advantages, both physically and mentally[2], [4], [5]. Apart from contributing to the purification, hydration, detoxification, moisturisation, and rejuvenation of skin, the significance of daily facial treatment in helping skin to have better skin absorption has also been reported. Some customers find it difficult to determine and decide on the right facial treatment for their skin. There are many types of facial treatment offered by different beauty stores, such as hydrating facial, brightening facial, anti-aging facial, and acne facial. Although some therapies are proprietary with only a few variations, different methods and procedures are often combined to produce a certain result, such as skin smoothing or lightening[1]. Every facial treatment prefers a specific name for each treatment, which can be quite confusing for most customers. Moreover, these specific names are often included in the branding and marketing of facial treatment[6].

It is not easy for us to consistently maintain a certain standard of perfection for skin, health, and body. Therefore, customers consider facial treatment to acquire skin care and skin health. Good service quality affects customer satisfaction. Before facial treatment begins, an aesthetician would first examine the skin conditions, such as blackheads, sun damage, dryness, or ageing, to decide the best way to handle or treat them. There is a long-standing misunderstanding when it comes to facial treatment. Many associate the idea of facial treatment to lavish and glamorous service and expect to experience it for a few times only in their lifetime. However, facial treatment is a crucial tool to preserve good skin condition and attain good feeling.

In addition, customers have certain expectations from a facial treatment, such as the preparation for the treatment, the products used, and the equipment used for different types of facial treatment. As a precaution, customers must inform their aesthetician if they have any skin allergies during the skin consultation before proceeding to any treatment. This ensures customer satisfaction and prevents any negative implication due to skin allergies. Skin consultation is also part of the facial treatment services (apart from facial treatment) offered to customers[7]. A comprehensive skin check that includes detailed skin evaluation is performed to create a personalised skin care system and relevant resources and information of managing or improving skin conditions are presented.

Facial treatment is essential for most people in their daily life, regardless of gender. The skin texture and skin complexity vary for everyone; thus, the exact timing of routine facial treatment can be different. Skincare specialists usually recommend facial treatment for every three to four weeks. If customers undergo several facial treatment sessions within a few weeks, their skin may become over-stimulated, which is known as skin sensitisation[8]. As the benefits of facial treatment become more widely known, facial treatment for skin maintenance is no longer considered as an excessively indulgent treatment. Facial treatment does not provide cure but can be essentially preventive to maintain healthy skin.

As an integral part of one's self-confidence, it is very important to take care of the skin. Every customer has the right to be satisfied or dissatisfied with the result of facial treatment. In that case, the best way to ensure customer satisfaction is to seek for authorised facial treatment centres.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Customer Satisfaction

Customers play a really important role to ensure the sustainability of business and marketing. Having strong relationships with customers is a perfect way to build customer satisfaction and retain customers[9]. No business can be competitive in this modern marketplace without an accurate understanding of what needs to be measured and how to collect, analyse, and use data as a strategic tool to drive the business[10]. Since customer satisfaction is a subjective and non-quantitative condition, quantitative measurement is not reliable and sampling and statistical analysis are required.

The level of customer satisfaction can be measured through the purchase cycle and subsequent receipt of products and services in a customer satisfaction survey—customers can express how they feel about their service contact, prior purchase, and overall purchase experience according to a five-point Likert scale with the endpoints of “highly satisfied” and “highly unsatisfied”. Accordingly, satisfaction itself refers to different factors of customer relationship—for examples, satisfaction towards a given product or service[11], satisfaction towards a continuing business partnership, and satisfaction towards the value for money ratio of a product or service[12]. Defining and recognising customer satisfaction can help any business to recognise improvement opportunities for the products and services and serve as the basis for success evaluation and reward systems.

In fact, there are various ways to ensure customer satisfaction. Firstly, business should understand the needs of customers. A successful business would maintain its relationship with customers based on the gathered information of customer need and any improvement required for its products or services[13]. Additionally, a business must always be open to customer feedback on their needs and suggestions in order to find effective solutions to address any customer-related problem. Besides that, a business should take the time to know more about each customer and provide personalised services to all customers and make them feel important and valued[12]. Adding to that, a business should also benchmark the level of customer satisfaction in order to evaluate its performance with the competitors' performance. For competitive advantages, a business should make effort to effectively improve and maintain good customer satisfaction, such as setting up a comprehensive and readily accessible website or timely response and delivery to customers[11].

Customer satisfaction encourages customer loyalty[14]. Customers would continue to purchase from the same brand as long as the business maintains trusting and trustworthy relationships with customers. Through trust, customers may continue to appreciate, use, and even campaign for the brand. However, the presence of dissatisfied customers are inevitable in business. In order to maintain a profitable service-oriented business, it is necessary to consider customer dissatisfaction because the negative effects of customer dissatisfaction can be rather substantial[15]. Customers respond to negative experience differently. Not all customers would communicate their frustration in the same manner; thus, it is important to understand different categories of dissatisfied customers. Customers who display a clear sense of disillusionment can be difficult to handle because their dissatisfaction can typically override reasonable discussion on why they are not satisfied[16]. These customers show strong feeling of dissatisfaction. However, there are also the opportunistic, disgruntled customers—they are not really dissatisfied but make complaints for minor reasons and usually seek for financial compensation. There are also customers who are truly unhappy with their encounter and include suggestions for improvement in their complaints.

Considering the profile of unsatisfied customers, a business must follow a comprehensive approach and accept any errors made[10]. After all, dissatisfied customers can potentially become loyal customers when their concerns are properly addressed. There are ways to improve customer dissatisfaction. For instance, a business should be attentive to the customer needs—even if the customer complaint is general, the business should take the time to make the customer feel heard and understand the reality of the situation[17]. When customers are encouraged to provide feedback, the business can gain valuable insights on how they can effectively deal with

the highlighted problems and follow up steps with customers (e.g. make a phone call or email to know how customers feel after the necessary action is taken and encourage their return).

This study aimed to gain a better understanding of how the psychological and emotional dimensions of service quality can influence customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is highly important for the well-being of the business, as customers aim to achieve value for money when they purchase a product or service. The perception of customer satisfaction, including emotional and customer-related aspects, is effective for a business to target customers.

2.2 Service Quality

Service quality represents the value of service to the customers. It is essentially subjective because it is driven by the customers' requirements, expectations, and perceptions[18]. In a general way, the measurement of service quality entirely depends on the context and promise of the brand and dimensions of service quality, which vary by industry. For the facial treatment industry, customers do not choose facial treatment solely based on price, but often on the service quality[19]. Studies have shown that customers pay more for a service that they believe to be well-produced or exceed the standard. This is important because customers expect to receive a quality product or service. There are five dimensions of service quality[20], [21] in order to achieve customer satisfaction and equate the perceived quality with their demand.

Firstly, reliability is the ability to efficiently deliver the promised service. This means that the promises on production, availability of equipment, problem resolution, and pricing of the business are fulfilled. Secondly, assurance is described as the awareness of employees' courtesy and ability to inspire their faith and confidence. This dimension may be particularly important for services that are viewed by customers as important. Another dimension of service quality is linked to tangibles that are the physical characteristics of the service provided, such as the appearance of the structure, cleanliness of the equipment, and appearance of the staff. Meanwhile, as for empathy, services can be carried out entirely according to the established requirements[22]. The employees' ability to convey care and genuine concern to their customers is a measure of empathy. Last but not least, responsiveness is the willingness to assist and provide quick service to the customers. This dimension of service quality emphasises customers' demands, questions, complaints, and issues with attention and timelessness.

The quality of a product or service can affect customer satisfaction, including how a business is operated and improved[23]. For business success, the role of an organisation in optimising the available resources should be recognised. Great service quality that meets business goals and needs ensures that customers receive the right service, which also benefits the business in terms of profits[17]. As the value of customer satisfaction should never be overlooked, a business should do more to ensure that its customers are treated well.

The measurement of service quality is linked to consistency, particularly the testimonials of past customers, which is one of the strategies that should be considered by the facial treatment industry[24]. The top ten positions in the websites for facial treatment that are based on the testimonials of regular customers are commonly targeted because these positions reflect the certified standard of facial treatment service by skin specialists. It is common for customers to look only at websites that display the highest ranking with positive testimonials of customers from diverse backgrounds. Facial treatment testimonials enable them to enhance their service quality that may lead to changes in facial treatment efficiency[25]. Besides that, the physical perception of facial treatment is essential to achieve customer satisfaction. Over-the-top interior design, which can be viewed as overwhelming, unique, or welcoming, can affect facial treatment customers who want to feel relaxed and chilled. Adding to that, no company is perfect and there should always be services available to encourage customers to make suggestions or complaints[26]. There should be a simple and straightforward way for customers to express their feeling, especially if they have bad experience with the product or service, for the organisation to effectively solve their issues in order to achieve customer satisfaction.

2.3 Brand Image

Brand image is how consumers view a brand. In simple terms, brand image refers to how well a product or service is received in the market based on the customers' responses to the product or service[27]. Brand image is also an intangible aspect of a brand that can be developed and the interpretation of brand elements in terms of name, logo, signature, and slogan. A business reflects brand, employees, and marketing materials. Meanwhile, a brand basically represents the company's promise to customers[28].

Branding is a key aspect of any business. Branding can reach many people across numerous offline and online platforms, which encourage customers to be aware of the products or services offered. Organisations that successfully rely on their brand can differentiate themselves better from their competitors and boost their marketing[9]. Conversion is one of the most crucial marketing fields, where a good brand research can have an

impact. Successful branding tends to encourage potential customers to purchase products or services[29]. The most effective way to develop repeat business is to remind customers of their favourable perception of the brand through their previous experience with the brand. Regardless of the advertising platform used, there is very little time to catch the interest of customers and influence their decision-making.

Brand image is important to customers, as people love sharing, especially when it comes to their favourite brand. However, customers cannot share a brand that they are not familiar with. A strong brand helps customers to know what to expect when they purchase the products or services, whereas a consistent and clear brand would make customers feel at ease. Brand image allows the business to communicate with its customers in an emotional way[30]. As buying is an emotional experience, having a strong brand would help customers feel good at an emotional level when they are involved in the business. In addition, a brand provides safety to customers. For example, customers are more likely to choose a national brand over a local brand because a brand provides protection and minimises the risk of disappointment. Lastly, a brand can offer the tranquillity of mind. Customers want convenience, joy, and fulfilment when they use the products and services that they purchase[31]. When the products and services consistently provide great experience, customers would feel the brand is trustable and offer reassurance.

2.4 Trust

In any business or personal relationship, trust is a critical factor. If a company has a good trust-based foundation, customers can be confident that the company is established and nurtured with honesty and integrity. In a business environment with customer expectations and intense competition, customer trust is not only critical but also a mark of distinction that can greatly affect a business[32]. The first way to develop customer trust is by improving the safety of customers. Customers should feel safe and secured with the services provided[33]. Facing a problem while receiving the services may affect customer trust; however, if the problem is properly and efficiently dealt with, the business can be seen as reliable. It is also important to ensure business transparency from the initial contact with customers without any misleading sales, marketing, and claims of the products or services offered in order to gain customer trust[34]. These aspects of business should be clearly presented to set the exact expectations of customers.

Trust creates customer satisfaction. Happy customers can be equated to real customers. After gaining customer trust, these customers would remain loyal and repurchase the products or services offered or seek for upgrade or other new products or services offered under the same brand[34]. Any loss of customer trust can seriously damage the business relationships with customers. Therefore, it is crucial to track customer satisfaction and improve any problematic areas. Despite the wide selection of choices offered, customers today consider easy access to online services[35]. A design can subconsciously influence how customers view a website and how much they can trust the information presented. Businesses that offer online chat, telephone consultation, and personal services can ensure that their customers feel secured and trust in the products or services offered and maintain long-term relationships with these businesses.

It is important to build trust for marketing. Customers are the main business assets and contribute to the purpose of the business. Businesses need to retain their existing customers and use their relationships with these customers to attract new customers[36]. As a business gains trust from customers, the business is more likely to be recommended to other customers since customers are more likely to recommend a trusted, credible business to other customers. Building trust helps businesses to develop marketing through word of mouth. Moreover, businesses have to manage their reputation. Another essential aspect of trust lies in strong social media advertising to provide customers with real and relevant information, including regular updates through various social media platforms[37]. This is a real-time approach to achieve the results of the search engine ranking. The reputation of managing a business is important since this involves what other customers think about the business. In addition, digital marketing strategy combined with instant search approach must be accomplished for long-term business survival. Good local findability is another important consideration to produce excellent results for online marketing.

Finally, trust enhances customer satisfaction and brand awareness. A customer is more likely to retain and repeat purchase based on trust in the brand. Additionally, the value of customer trust is higher than the average of their first purchase as customers tend to spend more on recurring purchases than new customers[17]. In order to encourage customer trust, there are no loopholes or shortcuts but it is a straightforward process that involves giving customers priority and attentive customer service.

2.5 Price

There are several implications in the future achievement when it comes to establishing the price of products and services[38]. Knowing how pricing affects the business model can help businesses to choose the appropriate

price level. Setting the price does not necessarily involve optimising the margins at all costs but most businesses set their price to compete, change market share, or share or create different profit scenarios[39]. The role of price in business competition involves setting the price of each unit sold or the total market share for optimum profitability. Price can be set to simply remain in the market or to deter competitors from joining or growing their market share. The increasingly competitive market competition, particularly comparison shopping, requires businesses to track the pricing strategy of their competitors in order to set competitive prices in order to achieve the requisite competitive edge in the marketplace[6]. Online prices are easy to compare and customers can easily find out the monetary value of each product.

Price is an important factor in determining how customers perceive the value of a product or service and the most significant factor in customer purchase decision. The role of price is one of the major elements of marketing strategy[40]. As a result, the right type of pricing strategy can help businesses to achieve their goals. Price must be appropriately set based on several factors, such as demand, profits, market share, and competition. Factors like product place and marketing may influence expenditure but the price factor may be the only factor that generates revenue. For most customers, higher price reflects better overall quality of the product and service[41]. Price adjustments are often part of special offers to reduce short-term costs by attracting customer interest towards the product or service. Businesses must be mindful of their attempt to change prices too often because the constant rise and fall in prices would condition their customers to withhold their purchase and expect price reduction.

A pricing strategy can be made or broken to satisfy customers. A reasonable pricing strategy positively affects customer satisfaction and makes it easier if there is a need to increase the price. Successful pricing practices, such as charging reasonable prices, stabilising prices, and retaining fixed prices, can have a positive impact on brand image and company reputation[42]. Higher price may intuitively reduce customer satisfaction. Nevertheless, customers enjoy reasonable prices, not just lower prices. If the price set is rational and correlates to the value that product or service offered, customers would establish a loyal and trustworthy relationship with the brand. A price that is not excessively high or low reflects a positive message of the product or service quality and the importance of the purchase. Although price reduction is typically one of the simplest means to improve customer satisfaction, customers may question the quality of a product or service if the price set is lower than the price set by competitors[43]. They may be more aware of potential weakness or feel that the product or service is not exceptional or worthwhile.

Accordingly, pricing objective represents the general business goals to be achieved through pricing. One of the pricing objectives involves reaching the target return on investment or revenue. The prices of the products and services offered are often set to maximise profits[44]. The prices set must be competitive in order to prevent price war or to maintain a stable profit level. Besides that, another pricing objective is to ensure market penetration to attract the most customers. A market penetration strategy can be effective if businesses can quickly boost their profits, increase unit costs, and purposely reduce prices for market entry[45]. This goal involves charging the lowest price possible for pricing buyers. As pricing objective is set also to maintain the image and reputation of the business in the market.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methodology used in this study, including the development of hypotheses. This chapter also includes the research design, data collection tools, target population, and sampling. Overall, this study aimed to identify the influence of several independent variables, specifically (1) service quality, (2) brand image, (3) trust, and (4) price on customer satisfaction (as dependent variable) in the case of facial treatment in Malaysia. The quantitative approach was applied to establish evidence and discover study trends based on observable data. Unlike qualitative methods, quantitative methods for data collection, which include different survey methods (e.g. digital survey and paper survey), are deemed more organised. data collection was made through questionnaires from the month of January 2020 to March 2020. 10 beauty centres in Kuala Lumpur was selected and each of them provide at least 50 list of their most recent customers for the survey. Out of 500 questionnaires distributed, only 256 was acceptable for data processing. The rest was rejected due to missing data and error.

Using Google forms, the online survey was conducted for this study, which involved randomly selected regular facial service customers in Malaysia, regardless of their race. In particular, almost 500 customers were contacted but only 256 customers responded. The developed questionnaire consists of six sections, where the first section involves the socio-demographic information of respondents (i.e. gender, age, highest education level, and occupation) whereas the remaining sections focus on customer satisfaction, service quality, brand image, trust, and price. For these sections, the respondents were required to provide their views according to the five-point

Likert scale with the endpoints of “strongly disagree” (1) and “strongly agree” (5). All collected data were analysed using SmartPLS to prove the proposed theories and structure. Besides that, this study also collected secondary data from articles, journals, related databases, and the Internet.

IV. FINDINGS

This study uses the PLS analysis technique with the SmartPLS Program. From the results of data processing, PLS analysis can be done by evaluating the structural equation model. In this evaluation, there are two basic evaluations. First, evaluating the measurement model (outer model) to find out the validity and reliability of indicators that measure latent variables; the instrument validity and reliability test criteria in this study refer to discriminant validity, convergent validity, and composite reliability. Second, assess the inner model or structural model to see the relationship between constructs, the significance value and the R-square of the research model. Testing Inner model in PLS analysis is done through bootstrap resampling.

Hair et al., (2014) opined that if the Cronbach alpha is less than 0.60, the study data is considered poor, while it is acceptable at 0.70 whereas, for Cronbach alpha over 0.80 is considered to be more reliable. In agreement with Nunnally (1978), the value of Cronbach’s alpha should be 0.700 or above. According to Gerrard, Cunningham, and Devlin, (2006), some of the studies also considered 0.600 as an acceptable value. In this study, the study of Cronbach’s alpha is more than 0.9, which is considered to be highly reliable as the value is more than 0.70.

No	Construct	Cronbach’s alpha
1	Brand Image	0.984
2	Customer satisfaction	0.948
3	Price	0.906
4	Service quality	0.983
5	Trust	0.940

Measurement model is an assessment of the validity and reliability of research variables. There are three criteria for assessing the outer models namely discriminant validity, composite reliability, and convergent validity. Based on the three criteria for measuring the measurement model from the results *bootstrapping* in the PLS method, testing the measurement model for each indicator that reflects the construct or latent variable can be explained as follows.

Apart from a series of assessments on reliability and validity of all the reflective items and constructs used in the study. This study finds it essential to further assess on its discriminant validity that is complementary to the prior assessments. Testing *discriminant validity* in research using score *square root of average* (AVE) to check (testing) whether the research instrument is valid in explaining or reflecting latent variables. Discriminant validity used is square root of average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}). If the square root of the average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}) value of each variable is greater than the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables, the instrument variable is said to be valid discriminant.

Table 4.2 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

No	Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
1	Brand Image	0.764
2	Customer satisfaction	0.736
3	Price	0.781
4	Service quality	0.734
5	Trust	0.807

Test results in Table 4.2 show that the value of average variance extracted (AVE) are more than 0.5. According to Hair, Sarstedt, & Ringle (2017) the average variance extracted (AVE) of each latent construct should 0.5 or higher. All constructs showed a satisfactory which explained more than 50% of variances of its items that ranges from 0.734 to 0.807.

The result from the square root of average variance extracted (\sqrt{AVE}) values of all variables are greater than the correlation between latent variables and other latent variables so that the instruments of each variable are valid

discriminant. In compliance to the Fornell-Larker’s criterion this study is keen to report that the constructs and items used in this study had confirmed its discriminant validity.

Convergent validity measures the validity of an indicator as a measure of construct, which can be seen from outer loading. From the value outer loading, it can also be interpreted as the contribution of each indicator to the latent variable. Outer loading of an indicator with the highest value means that the indicator is the strongest measure of the latent variable in question. More clearly follows the results of the analysis and evaluation of measurement models for each research variable.

Table 4.3 Outer Loading Each Indicator

	Brand Image	Customer Satisfaction	Price	Service Quality	Trust
BI1	0.860				
BI10	0.873				
BI11	0.868				
BI12	0.893				
BI13	0.904				
BI14	0.879				
BI15	0.884				
BI16	0.887				
BI17	0.877				
BI18	0.880				
BI19	0.846				
BI2	0.850				
BI20	0.918				
BI3	0.902				
BI4	0.855				
BI5	0.852				
BI6	0.893				
BI7	0.855				
BI8	0.865				
BI9	0.836				
CS1		0.804			
CS2		0.855			
CS3		0.899			
CS4		0.809			
CS5		0.828			
CS6		0.860			
CS7		0.906			
CS8		0.897			
PR1			0.913		
PR2			0.908		
PR3			0.916		
PR4			0.792		
SQ1				0.756	
SQ10				0.856	
SQ11				0.887	
SQ12				0.883	
SQ13				0.881	
SQ14				0.869	
SQ15				0.855	
SQ16				0.876	
SQ17				0.810	
SQ18				0.863	
SQ19				0.864	
SQ2				0.829	
SQ20				0.876	
SQ21				0.882	

SQ22				0.841	
SQ3				0.815	
SQ4				0.811	
SQ5				0.848	
SQ6				0.859	
SQ7				0.925	
SQ8				0.877	
SQ9				0.875	
TR1					0.910
TR2					0.912
TR3					0.894
TR4					0.885
TR5					0.889

All indicators in each variable have value outer loading above 0.70, which means that the indicators are valid and able to measure latent variables.

Composite reliability tests the value reliability between the indicators of the construct that constitutes it. Results are composite reliability said to be good, if the value is above 0.70. Test results of composite reliability the measurement model are presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Composite Reliability of Constructs

No.	Construct	Composite Reliability
1	Brand Image	0.985
2	Customer satisfaction	0.957
3	Price	0.934
4	Service quality	0.984
5	Trust	0.954

Based on the test results in Table 4.4 obtained the value of composite reliability of all variables above 0.70. These results mean that the six latent variables analyzed have good composite reliability and it is concluded that all instruments used in this study have met the criteria or are suitable for use in the measurement of the five latent variables: brand image, customer satisfaction, price, service quality, and trust.

The following table showed the result of direct hypotheses. The result supported three hypotheses out of four. Brand image, service quality, and trust have direct effect on customer satisfaction; on the other hand, only trust don't have direct effect on customer satisfaction.

Table 4.5 Path coefficient on relationships

Relationship	Original sample (β)	T Statistics	P-Values	Decision
Brand Image -> Customer satisfaction	0.278	2.182	0.030	Supported
Price -> Customer satisfaction	-0.062	0.810	0.418	Not Supported
Service quality -> Customer satisfaction	0.278	2.045	0.041	Supported
Trust -> Customer satisfaction	0.309	2.024	0.043	Supported

Based on table 4.5 explains the assessment of relationship between brand image, price, service quality, trust and customer satisfaction. The value of path coefficient for brand image to customer satisfaction was β 0.278, which is considered as medium magnitude identification. According to Cohen (1988) indicates the magnitude of the path coefficient as small (0.02), medium (0.15) and large (0.35). The result of t-value and p-value shows that the relationship between brand image and customer satisfaction are significant because the value of t-value is 2.182 and p-value is 0.030. The result shows significant and supported because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05.

The value of path coefficient for price to customer satisfaction was β -0.062, which is considered as small magnitude. The result of t-value and p-value shows that the relationship between price and customer satisfaction are not significant because the value of t-value is 0.810 and p-value is 0.418 which less than cutoff of 1.96 and *p*-value that is more than 0.05.

For service quality to customer satisfaction the path coefficient value was β 0.278, which is considered as medium magnitude. The result of t-value and p-value shows that the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction are significant because the value of t-value is 2.045 and p-value is 0.041. The result shows significant and supported because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05.

Lastly, the result of relationship between trust and customer satisfaction showed that the relationship are significant. The path coefficient value for trust and customer satisfaction was β 0.309 that is considered as large magnitude. The result of t-value and p-value shows that the relationship between trust and customer satisfaction are significant because the value of t-value is 2.024 and p-value is 0.043. The result shows significant and supported because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results show that there are at least 3 main factors that need to be given priority in order to meet the customer expectations and leading to customer satisfaction. It was highlighted that brand image, service quality and price are among the vital elements that service provider must focus in servicing their customer. Price was not significant in this study and one possible reason is because it matches with the customers' behavior. It was mentioned by [47] that customer accept the fact that price and value may come together. High prices may have reflected to high quality and premium services. Customer in 21st century is more knowledgeable as they have access to information. They have more choices in making decision. As such, prices is no longer become the surprise elements in getting high quality services.

Service provider need to ensure that they communicate well to customers and try to understand their expectations. Understanding customer expectations may lead to customer satisfaction. It was also highlighted by many past researchers that service provider must focused in giving more information about their products and avoid any hidden charges that may lead to negative customer experiences.

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